

"Tu-ub": Culture-based Folk Care Practice Among Cebuanos

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ABSTRACT

This study conducted an in-depth discovery and analysis on "tu-ub" or "himasmu" as a culture-based health care practice among Cebuanos in the province of Cebu. Mini-ethnonursing method was utilized to investigate the generic-folk practice. Utilizing the researcher as an instrument, the researcher observed and interviewed ten general informants purposively chosen from the pool of potential informants. Multiple observations and interviews were done among the six key informants (Tambalans=4; Lay=2) to triangulate and capture the most holistic feature of "tu-ub". To facilitate in the in-depth discovery and analysis process, the following Culture Care Enablers of Madeleine Leininger were utilized: (1) Observation-Participation-Reflection; (2) Stranger to Trusted Friend; (3) Sunrise Model; and (4) Specific Domain of Inquiry. Leininger's four-phase Ethnonursing Qualitative Data Analysis was utilized to facilitate a systematic data analysis. Qualitative results revealed that variations of the procedure of the practice rely on the availability of resources in the area. Procedures in the rural area were more detailed and complex since the resources were readily available. Procedures in the urban area were simple since the resources were limited and alternatives were utilized. "Tu-ub" was believed to be effective among Cebuanos to treat: (1) the different forms of "pasmu"; (2) "panuhut"; (3) bipolar disorder; (4) ringworm; and (5) mouth sores. Scientific explanation based from content analysis of relevant literature suggested technical benefits associated with induced sweating. However, this needs to be reevaluated in a more controlled setting. "Tu-ub" was compared to: (1) "Thermae" (Romans); (2) "Onsen" (Japanese); (3) "Banya" (Russians); (4) "Inipi" (American Indians); (5) Sauna (Finnish); and (6) "Hamam" (Turkish). It was observed that skin burns might occur when "tu-ub" was wrongly done. A recommended procedure was drafted. Western forms of treatment (medical) though believed to be effective, genuine and beneficial were less prioritized.

Background of the Study

"Cultural imposition remains a major serious and largely unrecognized problem in nursing as a result of cultural ignorance, blindness, ethnocentric tendencies, biases, racism, and other factors... If human beings are to survive and live in a healthy, peaceful and meaningful world, then nurses and other health care providers need to understand the cultural care beliefs, values and lifeways of people in order to provide culturally congruent and beneficial health care." Madeleine Leininger, 1978

Recently, there is an increase demand for culturally grounded care (Andrews & Boyle, 2008). The goal is to prepare nurses to be educated, sensitive, and proficient provider of care for people with different or similar lifeways, values, beliefs, and practices in meaningful, explicit, and beneficial ways (Leininger & McFarland, 2005). Awareness and sensitivity on the different generic care practices among Cebuanos, like "tu-ub", will help health care professional understand the practice and arrive in providing culture-specific interventions. Care is embedded as an integral part of culture, and health care professionals are challenged to understand both together in the practice.

Though the imperial medical and scientific concepts of care are important to nurses, generic-folk care philosophy will help enrich an effective nursing knowledge. Both needs to be identified to provide assistive, supportive and facilitative care for the health and well being of clients of specific culture.

Theoretical Framework

"Professional caring... necessitates the use of cultural concepts, principles, theoretical ideas and research findings to reflect upon and guide actions and decisions." Madeleine Leininger, 1978

Nurses are challenged to integrate the generic-folk system and the professional system in nursing care. According to Leininger, as cited by Tomey and Allgood (2002), nursing acts as a bridge between both systems. This is to arrive in generating research knowledge by: (1) discovering substantive knowledge; and (2) applying the knowledge to practice (Leininger, 1991, 1995). This stimulates nurses to design nursing actions and decisions using new knowledge and culturally based ways to provide meaningful and satisfying holistic care (Leininger, 1991 as cited by Sitzman & Eichelberger, 2004).

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of Theoretical Framework based from the middle part of Leininger's Sunrise Model Enabler

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of the study was to analyze the culture-based practice of "tu-ub" among Cebuanos.

Specifically, the study attempted to answer the following questions:

1. How was "tu-ub" practiced among Cebuanos?
2. Basing from the content analysis of relevant literature, what benefits can be derived from the practice?

Methodology

Mini-ethnonursing method was utilized to investigate practice of "tu-ub" among Cebuanos as a generic-lay form of treatment. The "big-net approach" was utilized to determine ten general informants purposively chosen from the pool of potential informants. From the ten general informants, six key informants were chosen purposively (Tambalans=4; Lay=2). Multiple observations and interviews were done to triangulate and confirm the gathered data and arrive in credible, confirmable, and transferable findings.

To facilitate in the in-depth discovery and analysis process, the Culture Care Enablers of Madeleine Leininger were utilized. Observation-Participation-Reflection Enabler facilitated in arriving in authentic data saturation. The Stranger to Trusted Friend Enabler helped in establishing trust and rapport with participants. The Sunrise Model Enabler guided the inquiry process. The Specific Domain of Inquiry Enabler provided direction and limits of the study (Leininger & McFarland, 2005).

The Leininger's four-phase Ethnonursing Qualitative Data Analysis was utilized to facilitate a systematic data analysis (Polit & Beck, 2008). Content analysis of relevant literature supplemented the researcher's analysis.

Findings

"Tu-ub" as Treatment for "Pasmu", "Panuhut", Skin Diseases and Mouth Sores. "Tu-ub" or "panghimasmu" was usually the "tambal" (cure) for "pasmu", "panuhut" (collective term for stress and other gas-related discomforts), skin diseases like "bun-i" (ringworm) and "lu-as sa baba" (mouth sores).

"Pasmu" was based in the concept of "init" (heat) and "bugnaw" (cold) and how the blending of these two can result in illnesses (Wikipedia, 2008). According to McBride (2001), Basilgo (1994) and Licauco (1982), "tu-ub" or "panghimasmu" was a steaming ritual and a faith healing practice to achieve "timbang".

"Pasmu" has also been a very common ailment encountered by Tambalan-A as complaints by her patients. She could not present a certain explanation about this type of illness. However, she enumerated

various symptoms that she had observed in her practice. She stated that if a person experienced "pasmu" then that person will suffer from moderate to severe headache, loss of appetite with or without fever. She also identified several types of "pasmu". "Pasmu sa init" was referred to the "pasmu" caused by exposure to the sudden change of weather. For example a client who had been walking around in a very hot day and suddenly exposed to a very cool breeze. She assumed that exposure to this weather could cause discomfort. "Pasmu sa bugnaw" was referred to the "pasmu" caused by ingesting extremely cold food when the body was not ready for intake of cold substances. This included: (1) eating iced candy; (2) eating ice cream; (3) drinking iced water; or (4) drinking cold sodas or drinks. Lastly, "pasmu sa ka-un" happened when there was irregular food intake. Usually, this person had already passed hunger caused by missing meals or skipping meals. There was no scientific explanation provided by the Tambalan. She claimed, that to cure these ailments "tu-ub" or "himasmu" could be done.

"Tu-ub" as Treatment for Psychiatric Disorder. The researcher happened to talk with the informant Tambalan-A's son. He unselfishly shared how his mother treated him with his mental disorder. He was admitted in the ward XII of Vicente Sotto Memorial Medical Center for six years. Diagnosed with bipolar disorder, he was taking lithium. He reported that he did not like taking it because it would make his tongue stiff and he could not talk well. He said that what made her well was the traditional way of treatment performed by his mother. Aside from "tayhup" (blowing), "hilut" (massage) and saying the "urasyun" (latin prayer), she frequently, performed "himasmu" to his son. The "himasmu" was a maintenance treatment so that there would be no relapse of the disorder. Informant Tambalan-A reported that she would know that her son will nearly reexperience the symptoms of bipolar disorder when she could see his son with "dagku kaayu ug singut" (diaphoresis).

"Tu-ub" Procedure Variations. There were many varied ways in doing the "tu-ub" or 'panghimasmu". The most common domestic procedure observed among urban Cebuanos was by cooking the "dukot" (burnt rice) with the food that causes the abdominal discomfort. When cooked, the person was placed over the "kaldiru" (cooking pot) while covering himself with a thick blanket. The person inhaled and felt the warmth of the smoke produced. The person then perspired and cure was believed to be realized.

"Panghimasmu" to treat "pasmu", in the rural area, could be done in several artistic ways. The commonalities in the different procedures were noted. Either rice or corn were overcooked and added with different types of chosen herbs and food that were believed to cause the "pasmu". The preparation would be placed near the body and the person experiencing the "pasmu" would position in any preferred form while covered with a thick blanket until diaphoretic. The preparation could be or eaten or not. Then cure was believed to be achieved.

Informant Tambalan-A also performed "himasmu" to her patients. She handed the researcher a piece of paper on how she performed "himasmu". She used two table spoons of "pinaig na ginaling na mais" (grounded corn), one and a half pieces of "mangga" (mango) leaves, one and a half pieces of "buungun" (pomelo) leaves, one table spoon of brown sugar, three pieces of "udlot sa laghub" (shoots or unopen leaves of ficus hauili bianco) and one cup of water. These ingredients were mixed together and heated to boil. However, other ingredients could be added. This could be the food that might have caused the "pasmu". It could be soft drinks, coconut or ice. This would be placed in the floor where the patient would sit beside the preparation. The patient would then cover himself with a thick blanket together with the preparation. The warmth from the preparation would be felt by the patient until diaphoretic. After two to three minutes, the patient would then orally consume the preparation.

Informant Tambalan-B also demonstrated the claimed proper method of doing "himasmu". She placed the plastic of ice in the cooking pot with one glass of water from the gallon. She then grilled the "dukot" until it smelled like "angtud" (roughly translated as aromatic). Then the grilled burnt rice was mixed with the cooked ice preparation in a pitcher then covered. Then she asked the researcher to place the researcher's "kutu-kutu" (epigastric area) over the pitcher as she covered the researcher with a thick blanket. It was observed that the researcher perspired heavily and she stated "nigawas na ang panuhot". In case of fever, when the client perspired heavily then the body temperature would be normal.

Tambalan-C presented another method which was different from the household procedure and other Tambalans practice. She taught the researcher her own procedure. She stated that the ice should be placed in a cooking clay pot with the overcooked rice (not steamed, cooked like rice crispies without oil or water) and one teaspoon of brown sugar. If the person experiencing the discomfort had intake of soft drinks, ice candy or ice cream, then what had been eaten would be added to the formula. Then the cooking clay pot would be covered with banana leaf when the formula was heated to boil. When boiled, would place the cooking clay pot containing the cooked formula in the floor and would remove the

banana leaf cover. The patient would then be asked to sit beside the cooking clay pot containing the cooked formula. She rationalized that there was no need to place the body over the preparation and the body should not be overheated with the smoking heat produced by the preparation to prevent possible burns. However, the client should cover himself with a thick blanket together with the preparation for two to three minutes. The moist found in the banana leaf used as cover would be wiped to the patient's forehead, face, chest and abdomen. She emphasized wiping away that moist produced by the body would eliminate the bad air that had caused the discomfort.

Tambalan-D presented a more safe procedure in doing the "tu-ub". In her demonstration, "tu-ub" was done by boiling the water. After boiling, the boiling pot was removed from the fire. The patient then, while assuming the fowlers position, was completely covered with a thick blanket. The pot containing the boiling water was then placed inside the thick blanket together with the patient. Its pot's cover was then opened to allow the steam to disperse. The affected part of the body was suspended above the pot of boiling water allowing the steam to moisten the area. She emphasized that the affected area should not be placed closely to the boiling preparation to prevent burns. She added that the facial area must not be suspended over the preparation.

"Tu-ub" in the rural and urban areas has both similarities and differences. Though practices were similar, differences were presented in the procedures and materials utilized. The differences in the procedures rely on the availability of resources in the area. Procedures in the rural area were more detailed and complex since the resources were readily available. Procedures in the urban area were simple since the resources were limited and alternatives were utilized.

Content Analysis of Relevant Literature on the Benefits of Induced Sweating. There were valid reasons why human beings have used sweat baths for hygienic and health purposes since the Stone Age. Most cultures around the world have their own versions of induced sweating procedures, whether it's the ancient Romans and their "Thermae" or the traditional Japanese "Onsen". The Russians call it "Banya", while native North American Indians call it "Inipi". The most prominent and most popular is the Finnish Sauna while the most notorious form is the Turkins "Hamam" (Pure Inside Out, 2007). The Cebuano version of the healing art of induced seating is the "tu-ub".

"Tu-ub" is found by the researcher to be beneficial. The researcher believed that it follows the same concept with convection and the benefits of sweating. When the body is having high temperature, "tu-ub" might help. The skin produces cool sweat to regulate the body's elevated temperature (Pure Inside Out, 2007). The sweat through convection is dispersed by air currents thus further loses an amount of heat (Kozier et al, 2004).

During any induced sweating procedure, the temperature of the skin would increase and the heart would beat faster, thus activating the circulation and oxygenates the cells, tissues and organs. In a short time, there was much perspiration, thus removing excess heat from the body and carrying away troublesome substances and impurities (Kozel, 1972). It also has the ability to transform toxins from lipid-soluble or oil-based, into-easier to eliminate-water-soluble forms. Sweat carries toxins out of the body and would flush them through the pores (Pure Inside Out, 2007).

The "tu-ub", just like any other sweating procedures, worked on the principle of generating abundant sweat to detoxify the body by removing toxic chemicals and metals faster. It relaxes the mind, leaving the body soothed and serene. Sweating effectively helps relieve mental fatigue and stress. It increases the body's ability to produce energy, which promotes healing and at the same time speeds up the metabolism. It is also believed that exposure of the skin to heat stimulates the production of white blood cells and strengthens the immune system. Sweating is the body's safe and natural way to heal. Scientists and doctors finally acknowledged what our ancestors instinctively knew, that regular sweating could restore good health through the elimination of toxins (Pure Inside Out, 2007).

Researchers' Observations, Analysis and Reflections. "Tu-ub" was believed to be effective among Cebuanos. Western forms of treatment though believed to be effective, genuine and beneficial were less prioritized. The practice was found by the researcher to have promising benefits with scientific basis. This did not involve fraud but needed to be reevaluated in a more controlled setting.

Conclusions

Provision of culturally competent nursing care to Cebuano clients practicing "tu-ub" can only occur when nurses considerably and competently incorporated the generic-folk practices into nursing care plans after considering the analysis of its technical benefits and danger.

Recommendations

Results of this study should be considered by nurses in their care decisions and actions. Cebuano clients practicing "tu-ub" should be careful and follow recommended procedures for safety. Replications are encouraged to confirm the results of this study and to supplement information not covered by this study. A more in-depth and controlled studies are encouraged utilizing a more sophisticated methodology not limited to qualitative design.

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